
Impact of Advance Technology in Sports in India

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15067334

Abstract:

Technology is a huge thing within sport, it varies from mobile phones, televisions, sport equipments and more, there is no doubt that the importance of the use of technologies has increased over the years, and since then, sports have become a globally activity, so are the decision that can change the result of an event. With the implementation of technology, correct decisions have been made, giving to the right team the winner place. The use of technology has its pros and cons but almost every sport now days is supported by it allowing to fans, athletes and judges, a more enjoyable environment while watching, playing or deciding a sport event such as [Tennis](#) or [Swimming](#). With implantation of modern cameras for instant replay, new materials for racquets as well as automatic heating system for pools and sophisticated swimsuit new techniques and rules are being used in order to preserve the authenticity of the olden sport, where the athletes make the effort to win a medal or a position in the history.

Keywords: *Technology, Equipments, Implementation, Environment, Authenticity etc.*

Introduction:

The recent development in technology is encouraging the development of sports in various dimensions. From the players' aspect, we find a better place for practice and skill development. From the spectators' point of view, we see the perfect use of technology in sports. Back in the day, we use to have a view or two of the sports played. There were limited cameras that can even properly zoom on the sportspersons and athletes. We have no high-definition feed of the channels that offer a 360-degree view of the sport's actions right away. We have come a long way in the development of technology related to sports. The athletes are faster and stronger than the previous generations. The coaches and managers now use tactical software platforms to analyze the performance of the sportspersons. They even use sensors to measure the vital functions of players during exercise sessions and field

actions. Previously, trainers and coaches had to follow extensive paperwork to find out the performance of a player or a sports team. Imagine how many things a coach had to keep in his mind regarding individual players. These days, we can design charts and graphs and can even get detailed reports offering deeper insights into individual or team performance. The principle of sports training depends on the latest technology used. Players wear sensors and GPS to monitor their movements. The management team can track the actions of players. The latest technology can also track how an athlete is performing on the field. The best types of shoes and sports gear are designed after comprehensive research and development to offer a better ground for better performance.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the technology changes in sports.
2. To study role of technology in sports.

Methodology of the Study:

The present study has been descriptive; the data for this study were obtained from secondary sources. The secondary data has been collected from various references which already existed in published form; part of the paper is based on literature review the method comprising of collecting all the available papers relating to the theme and selecting relevant papers/books for the review purpose.

Technology changes in sport:

Technology has assisted players and coaches in the field of education, quick recovery of athlete injuries, and their performance. Even coaches are upgraded, as previously they use white chalkboards, and now they use tablets for enhancing the ability to show play-by-play information of various situations. Coaches hold the ability to undertake side-by-side athlete comparison and the same help in imparting better coaching. The use of high-definition digital equipment permits coaches to see the right view and explore the mistakes with the aid of the frame option. Even athletes are taking benefit of advanced or new technology. For instance, the New Nike strobe eyewear supports players to gain a competitive advantage. This device is an integrated model, which permits the players to enhance their visual skills and ability to view better.

Equipment is highly improved in various sports nowadays. In football, helmets are introduced for stopping subdural hematoma and skull fractures. The new 360, feature of the helmet is the flexible face mask, which supports absorbing the energy, which comes in front of the helmet. Technology has assisted in revolutionizing

the way, in which one can design apparel as well as equipment. From uniforms to shoes to helmets to gloves and pads, sports equipment is higher functional and high-tech; going to any sporting event has become a different experience. As now scoreboards have also gone high definition, recreational devices like hitting machines and batting cages have become quite popular, and even fans have the accessibility to use Wi-Fi connection.

Increase use of technology has offered a better and more convenient opportunity for all athletes to quickly elevate their performance and skills. The team now holds the ability to see and understand the videos and can learn different forms and techniques. These technologies help athletes as well as coaches in viewing the game motions. Similar technology can also be used in considering the opposing team.

With technological improvement, coverage of sports is gone quite extensive, like never before. In the past, viewers had to choose a few channels to see the match; now there are a plethora of alternatives. A very platform, coverage is present, with a full replay of the match. In the past, missing any game implies that one has to wait for the morning when they can read the results in the newspaper. Now people can easily save, record or either replay the match footage.

Role of Technology in Sports:**Decision-making:**

Decisions taken by the umpire or referee can impact the results of the match. In particular cases, the direction of the game might get change with one decision. In the past few years, technology is increasingly used in various sports, which does not always help in the decision-making process. For instance, different external bodies like coaches, commentators, and the, which are in the position of scrutinizing decisions, usually access the latest technology like a replay or slow motion play from different

angles. In sports, the use of video technology is at the forefront of many discussions in the last few years. Few think it as negative than positive, as games are taking a long time due to the inclusion of video referrals, whereas else some believe that many game officials depend completely on technology and that they face challenges in making their decision. This belief held that there are improvements, which are still to be done, and the same can be just viewed as a benefit for enhancing the right decision making, and as the result of that, coaches, players, and fans don't move as hard it was done.

In the game of football, goal-line technology is increasingly implemented for the purpose of the track the position of the ball in connection with the goal line to remove the wrong decisions taken by the umpire. For example, FIFA had applied different goal lines technology like GoalRef, GoalControl, as well as Hawk-Eye which includes a high-speed video camera, and magnetic field-based technology. In the game of cricket, Hawk-Eye technology is used, which is a visual ball tracking software. This technology is employed in many Tests, Twenty20, and ODI matches since 2001. It also makes use of various smart replay technology for the purpose of recording camera feeds and for making them available in real-time, which helps the third umpire in taking the right decision in extreme situations like, disputed catches, no-balls, boundaries, and stumpings.

Ethical issues:

There are different ethical problems associated with the use of technology in sports, and there are many who debate about the place of technology in various sports. Different technologies like video replay and goal-line technology used for decisions are applied on the field and often impact sports and how the game is played. Advancement in technology has provided benefits to people having a disability. Changes related

to wheelchair prosthetics, and much more lead people with different disabilities to take part in sports and this can be considered as a significant achievement. The question which is often raised is how far the technology has gone. The highest ethical problem is linked with technology use in sports. It is important that technology should be utilized for enhancing the performance of games. It is true that audiences are interested in viewing improved performances; whereas else, athletes are interested in improving their performance. Performance improvement might go rare if the technology is not used in sports. Nevertheless, if the technology results in unfair or unethical competition, then its use should be limited. Another question raised is how the accessibility of technology has led to unfair competition. The ethical problems linked with technology use in sports cover-up access equity. It is true that obtaining technology is quite costly, mainly in the case of biomechanical analysis as well as physiological testing. Even though many types of equipment are quite expensive, and most of the competitors cannot afford to purchase technology, then, in that case, competition might go unfair, as there is inequity in technology accessibility. However, different sports competition includes clubs as well as athletes who can or cannot afford the use of technology. For example, major competitions like Champion League, A-League, etc. have a huge amount of money for accessing technology, and the same goes for leading individual sports like tennis and golf. In the case of international competitions, they fail to have a similar type of equity. In poor developing countries, individual athletes fail to afford advanced technologies, as compared to athletes coming from developed countries, mainly from countries in Australia, America, and England that place a high value on sports.

Conclusion:

There are other remarkable types of technologies used in sports and training. The training sessions are made more productive by measuring the physical aspects and output of players. The movements are tracked to analyze and make them better. These days, athletes and sportspersons use exclusive protective gear for better and safer performance. In fact, differently-abled athletes used prosthetics to perform and participate in national and international sports events. The importance of technology in sports is pretty much clear now. There are limitless possibilities for using different other technologies in different sports. From wearable to training tech gear, we observe how technology has been redefining sports exceptionally throughout the years.

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